

of this. After all, language is a verbal expression of culture. It conveys our experience as a people. This is why Mongolian contains a rich vocabulary surrounding animals and French is a go-to language for food. It is why in Japanese, refusing an offer sometimes requires about three lines (two of which may involve apologizing), when a simple English “No” might suffice in a similar situation. The American writer Rita Mae Brown once said, “Language is the roadmap of a culture. It tells you where its people come from and where they are going”. Beyond vocabulary and grammar rules, somewhere in the world, there is a group of wonderful people who use the language you are teaching in the classroom. They use it to buy milk, to chat with friends, to comment on Facebook statuses, to make songs and movies with. Their culture so beautiful, it can make the pages of a language textbook spring to lifeⁱⁱ

How to Learn English with Movies | Top 10 Best Films

Watching films is a fun way to improve your English! In this ESL guide, we will show you 10 of the best movies for studying English and give you tips and resources to help you learn English through films. Ready? Lights, camera, action!

Why learn English with films?

Watching films is a lot more fun than studying with a textbook! It can also be just as useful. Here is why sitting down with a movie in English will improve your fluency:

REAL ENGLISH – Textbooks are great for learning vocabulary or grammar, but nothing is better than listening to real native English. By watching British and American films, you can listen to native English actors speaking the language in a natural way. This will help you learn modern English and sound more like native speaker in terms of vocabulary and style.

BETTER PRONUNCIATION – Sometimes it can be hard to know how an English word is pronounced. Hearing native speakers in movies will teach you the correct way to say things. Dialogues in films also provide good examples of how sounds in words change in connected speech.

LIVE CONTEXT – When you learn a word, it can be difficult to remember what it means or how to use it. In films, words are used as part of a story and this context helps you to learn and remember them more effectively.

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NATIVE ACCENTS – Across Britain and America there are many different accents used to speak English. When watching films, you will hear many regional accents being used and this will help you to understand them better. Textbooks seldom provide information about English accents.

EXPLORE CULTURE – You can learn about the culture behind the language when you watch movies in English. Language and culture are closely connected. Why not study both at the same time by watching original filmsⁱⁱⁱ

What is realia?

Simply put, realia refers to authentic objects from real life that one uses in the classroom to teach a specific concept. Realia can be both physical and virtual, as long as it is something used in the real world (rather than created specifically for an ESL class).

Why use realia in the classroom?

Realia for ESL can make the learning experience more memorable and create connections between objects and vocabulary words or other language concepts. This can make it easier to recall information. For in-person classes, it adds a kinesthetic element for people who learn better with hands-on activities. For online classes, it provides a visual aid to engage students. Additionally, realia is more dynamic than a written word or flashcard used to teach a concept.

What are some examples of realia?

Realia can incorporate what's already in your classroom, such as a desk, chair, or poster. Or, it can be something you've brought from outside of class, like a collection of colorful brochures, a stuffed animal, tickets, or souvenirs you got while traveling. While any of these will work for both an in-person class or an online class (for the latter, simply hold the objects up to your screen), you can also make use of virtual realia in the online classroom. Virtual realia refers to authentic resources found online, such as advertisements, photographs, menus, receipts, or maps. Similar to using props to teach English online, incorporating realia into the virtual classroom engages students and makes for a livelier class.^{iv}

References

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iv <https://bridge.edu/tefl/blog/use-realia-esl-classroom/>